

A REVIEW ON FOG AND CLOUD COMPUTING

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Abstract—Fog and cloud computing have transformed various industries, including health monitoring, electronic appliance monitoring, space monitoring, real-time surveillance, and artificial intelligence. Fog nodes use interconnected smart devices and wearable sensors to gather, process, and analyze real-time health data, lowering latency and maintaining data privacy. The Cloud offers extensive infrastructure for secure storage and long-term health records.

In electronic appliance monitoring, fog nodes may gather and analyze real-time energy usage data, enhancing power grid stability and storing massive amounts of data. Fog nodes can also help with space monitoring by bringing data pre-processing closer to the source, minimizing communication latency, and allowing for more effective data analysis in the cloud. Edge devices and cloud-based video analytics algorithms can enhance real-time monitoring by pre-processing video data and detecting abnormalities. Combining AI with fog computing and cloud computing creates new opportunities for automated decision-making. Deep learning algorithms enable pattern recognition, predictive modelling, and anomaly detection, making fog and cloud computing essential for artificial intelligence, real-time surveillance, space monitoring, electronic appliance monitoring, and health monitoring.

Keywords—Cloud Computing, Fog Computing, Industrial Internet of Things, Mobile cloud computing, Mobile Edge Computing, Reinforcement Learning, Multi-Objectives Grey Wolf Optimizer, Proof of Concept

INTRODUCTION

In today's digital era, information technology plays a crucial role in our daily lives and various industries. However, the exponential growth of data and increasing demand for faster processing and real-time access have created significant challenges for traditional computing infrastructures. As a result, emerging technologies like fog computing and cloud computing have gained immense popularity as solutions for efficient data processing and storage.

Fog computing, also known as edge computing, is a decentralized computing architecture that extends cloud computing capabilities. It brings computation, networking, and storage resources closer to the data source, reducing latency and bandwidth requirements. This proximity to the data source enables faster processing, real-time analytics, and secure data transfer between devices. Therefore, it's an ideal solution for applications like the Internet of Things (IoT), smart cities, and autonomous vehicles.

On the other hand, cloud computing has revolutionized the way we access and manage data. By providing on-demand access to a vast network of servers and virtual resources, cloud computing offers scalability, flexibility, and cost-efficiency to individuals and businesses. It

allows users to store, retrieve, and process data remotely, eliminating the need for physical infrastructure while maintaining high availability and reliability.

The combination of fog computing and cloud computing brings benefits beyond what either technology can offer individually. Fog computing complements cloud computing by addressing its limitations, such as latency issues in real-time applications, and reducing network congestion. By moving computations closer to the edge, fog computing enables faster response times and reduced dependency on cloud resources.

In this project, we aim to explore the potential of fog computing and cloud computing in tackling the challenges and optimizing performance in data-intensive applications. We will examine the architecture, protocols, and algorithms involved in deploying fog computing and cloud computing systems. Furthermore, we will conduct experiments and simulations to evaluate the performance, scalability, and reliability of these systems in different use cases.

By the end of this project, we expect to have a comprehensive understanding of fog computing and its integration with cloud computing. We aim to provide insights into the benefits and challenges of deploying fog computing in real-world scenarios and offer recommendations for its effective implementation. Ultimately, our project aims to contribute to the advancement of fog computing and cloud computing technologies, paving the way for faster, more efficient, and secure data processing and storage.

A. Cloud Computing

Cloud computing is the Internet-based delivery of various services. Data storage, servers, databases, networking, and software are a few examples of the tools and applications that fall under this category.

B. FC (Fog Computing)

Fog computing is a dispersed computing infrastructure that moves data, processing power, storage, and applications between the cloud and data source, bringing cloud benefits closer to data creation and action, primarily for efficiency improvement.

C.IIoT (Industrial Internet of Things)

The term "Industrial Internet of Things," or "IIoT," describes a network of interconnected industrial devices. It belongs to the Internet of Things subset (IoT). The fact that linked devices on IIoT networks transmit data without requiring communication between people or between computers is what makes them unique.

D. MCC (Mobile cloud computing)

Cloud computing and mobile computing integrated on a wireless network is known as mobile cloud computing technology. High-quality programs may now be delivered and run on mobile devices, independent of the operating system, storage capacity, and computational requirements of the latter.

E. MEC (Mobile Edge Computing)

A concept known as Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) moves processing power closer to mobile devices at the network's edge. It reduces reliance on distant cloud servers by processing data locally, improving low-latency, high-bandwidth applications.

F. RL (Reinforcement Learning)

Algorithms that are trained to make judgments regarding resource allocation, task scheduling, and optimization in distributed computing environments—adapting to dynamic situations to enhance efficiency and performance—are the subjects of reinforcement learning in fog and cloud computing.

G.MGWO (Multi-Objectives Grey Wolf Optimizer)

Multiple-Objectives an algorithm for cloud-fog computing is called Grey Wolf Optimizer. By maximizing job scheduling, it lowers latency and energy usage.

H. PoC (Proof of Concept)

Before a suggested solution is fully deployed, a small-scale model or prototype is implemented as part of the Proof of Concept (PoC) process in fog and cloud computing to ensure its practical viability.

SL. NO.	TITLE	AUTHORS	DESCRIPTION	LIMITATION
1.	Security and Privacy in Fog Computing: Challenges[1]	MITHUN MUKHERJEE , RAKESH MATAM, LEI SHU, LEANDROS MAGLARAS , MOHAMED AMINE FERRAG, NIKUMANI CHOUDHURY AND VIKAS KUMAR	Due to fog computing's properties, there are new security and privacy issues. Fog computing's characteristics, including its large-scale geodistribution, mobility, and heterogeneity, make it impossible to use the security and privacy measures already in place for cloud computing. An overview of current privacy and security issues is given in this study, with a focus on fog computing. After that, this survey focuses on current research initiatives, unresolved problems, and emerging themes in cloud computing privacy and security.	Cloud computing security and privacy concerns are extensively researched; however, because of the unique features of fog computing and the larger number of fog devices at the network's edge, none of them are appropriate for fog computing. The purpose of this survey, in short, is to provide an overview of recent academic contributions and future research directions aimed at addressing various privacy and security problems in fog computing.
2.	Fog Computing in Healthcare–A Review and Discussion[2]	FrankAlexander Kraemer;Anders Eivind Braten; Nattachart Tamkittikhun; David Palma	In fog computing, network components communicate with the cloud and devices to carry out application-specific logic. This review examines fog computing in the healthcare industry, identifying use cases for applications and enumerating tasks particular to each. It highlights important healthcare computing jobs that can be enhanced by fog computing principles but necessitate higher network-tier processing because of data aggregation and wireless device limitations.	Fog computing allows various computer processes in ubiquitous healthcare applications to be offloaded between sensors and the cloud, which can be beneficial. It can lessen network burden, filter data, and adjust sensor requirements to standard interfaces. But to reap the full benefits, attention needs to move from specific use cases to all-encompassing architectures that take into account a range of deployment situations and application use cases.
3.	Tasks Scheduling and Resource Allocation in Fog Computing Based on Containers for Smart Manufacturing[3]	Luxiu Yin , Juan Luo and Haibo Luo	Fog computing, an extension of cloud computing, offers computational, storage, and network services in network edge networks. However, limited resources and low-delay services hinder its application. A new task scheduling model and algorithm are proposed to optimize task completion and reduce delays. The results show that these algorithms and reallocation schemes effectively reduce task delays and improve concurrency in fog nodes.	This paper introduces fog computing in smart manufacturing for real-time data analysis in assembly line terminal devices. Containers are designated as task units, and a novel task scheduling algorithm and resource reallocation scheme are designed to improve resource utilization and reduce task delays. Experiments show that the scheduling algorithm increases accepted tasks by 5% and reduces execution time by 10%. However, the paper ignores cloud resource finiteness and image placement issues, which need further attention.

4.	Secure Data Storage and Searching for Industrial IoT by Integrating Fog Computing and Cloud Computing[4]	Jun-Song Fu, Yun Liu, Han-Chieh Chao, Bharat K. Bhargava, Zhen-Jiang Zhang	Due to energy and storage capacity constraints, local storage is not suited for the massive amounts of data generated by the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT). The difficulties with data processing, safe storage, effective retrieval, and dynamic data gathering in the IIoT are covered in this paper. The integration of cloud computing and fog computing results in a flexible framework where time-sensitive data is kept locally and raw data is preprocessed by edge servers. The suggested structure increases IIoT data storage and retrieval security and efficiency, according to simulations and experiments.	This work proposes a fog computing and cloud computing-based secure, adaptable, and effective data storage and retrieval system. It tackles issues with dynamic data collection, searchable encryption, organization, and data refining. For privacy-preserving data search, the system consists of an index encryption approach based on the secure kNN algorithm and a retrieval feature tree. Nevertheless, the framework encounters obstacles such as restricted techniques for retrieving data, privacy issues, and the requirement for homomorphic encryption systems.
5.	Profiling Performance of Application Partitioning for Wearable Devices in Mobile Cloud and Fog Computing[5]	CLAUDIO FIANDRINO , NICHOLAS ALLIO , DZMITRY KLIASOVICH, PAOLO GIACCONE AND PASCAL BOUVRY.	In order to enhance wearable device capabilities, this study investigates the usage of mobile cloud computing (MCC) and fog computing (FC). Specifically, it looks at how to divide up mobile apps and transfer computationally demanding activities to the cloud or edge. The study benchmarks energy and execution time performance using an Android-based application, exposing architectural tradeoffs and offering recommendations for appropriate power management in Internet-of-things apps that are service-centric.	This article investigates application partitioning performance in mobile computing centres (MCCs) and field computing centres (FCs) using the TreeGlass Android application. The study found that different partitioning circumstances influence application design and communication media selection. Local computation is advantageous in FC with little communication overhead, whereas it is only advantageous in MCC if offloading costs become prohibitively expensive.
6.	Energy-Efficient Fair Cooperation Fog Computing in Mobile Edge Networks for Smart City[6]	Yifan Dong, Songtao Guo, Jiadi Liu, and Yuanyuan Yang	Building a smart city necessitates a heavy computing load and latency in the network, especially when using AI algorithms. A Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) paradigm called fog computing improves the user experience by being fair. An integrated optimisation problem is resolved, and a cooperative fog computing system is constructed. To achieve optimal fairness cooperation across fog nodes, a fairness cooperation algorithm (FCA) is developed. The findings indicate that FCA converges fast and uses less energy and time overhead.	In AI and IoT-enabled smart city systems, this research examines workload cooperative computation among fog nodes. The Fairness Cooperation Algorithm, which the authors present, optimises QoE and energy in a fair manner, producing a matrix that beats previous algorithms in terms of time and energy consumption.

7.	Offloading Mechanisms Based on Reinforcement Learning and Deep Learning Algorithms in the Fog Computing Environment[7]	DEZHEEN H. ABDULAZEEZ AND SHAVAN K. ASKAR	Fog computing, as a computing paradigm for Internet of Things devices, lowers latency and boosts system performance by shifting resource-intensive tasks to a fog or cloud layer with abundant resources. On the other hand, excessive request volumes may result in inefficiencies and lengthy lines. To tackle these problems, reinforcement learning (RL) was introduced; however, deep reinforcement learning (DRL) was created to combine RL with deep learning. This study divides the fog computing offloading techniques into three categories: value-based, policy-based, and hybrid-based algorithms.	By shifting computing resources to network edges, fog computing offers a viable way to lower network operating costs and enhance user device quality of service (QoS). Computation offloading involves moving resource-intensive operations from devices with limited resources to a fog or cloud server with abundant resources, thereby improving application performance and minimizing latency. This work provides a thorough investigation of offloading mechanisms in a fog computing environment using RL and DRL approaches. There were three types of algorithms used in the 56 research publications that made up the final selection: value-based, policy-based, and hybrid-based algorithms. When offloading schemas, DQN and Q learning were the most commonly used algorithms. Security, mobility, multi-objective mechanisms, implementation, workload prediction, optimal policy selection, and offloading modelling problems confront current fog offloading solutions.
8.	Multi-Objective Grey Wolf Optimizer Algorithm for Task Scheduling in Cloud-Fog Computing[8]	FATEN A. SAIF , ROHAYA LATIP , ZURINA MOHD HANAPI , AND KAMARUDIN SHAFINAH	Tasks are now being moved to cloud data centres and fog nodes due to the massive amount of data created by the IoT revolution. Nevertheless, these techniques necessitate work assignments and increase energy usage. In order to lower the delay and energy consumption associated with cloudfog computing, this study suggests using the Multi-Objectives Grey Wolf Optimizer (MGWO) algorithm. Modern algorithms are used to evaluate the algorithm's efficacy.	The MOP technique is used in the paper to analyse work scheduling challenges in a cloud-fog computing environment. It suggests using the MGWO algorithm to reduce the delay and energy consumption of QoS targets. Simulation findings reveal that MGWO beats other algorithms in terms of delay reduction and energy consumption. The study also looks into resource heterogeneity, which might impact resource utilisation and load imbalance. Future research could concentrate on optimising other goals and utilising AI for optimisation.
9.	Evolution of Emerging Computing paradigm Cloud to Fog: Applications, Limitations and Research Challenges[9]	Mohit Kumar, Kalka Dubey, Rakesh Pandey	The CoT's infrastructure is dispersed geographically, complex, and varied. The scalability and high latency of this data made it impossible for the standard cloud paradigm to handle. Fog computing is therefore utilized to process real-time applications nearer to data	Our goal going forward is to apply the resource scheduling technique for the fog computing environment, which significantly improves the QoS parameters and schedules real-time applications.

			sources and enhance network congestion resistance, energy efficiency, latency, and scalability.	
10.	On the Performance of Fog-Cloud Computing for Real-time Surveillance Applications[10]	Saleh Abdalla, Mohamed S. Hassan, Taha Landolsi, Ra'afat Abu-Rukba	This research aims to investigate the feasibility of fog computing as a platform for Internet of Things (IoT)-based real-time surveillance applications. In particular, we study and contrast the efficacy of a hybrid fog-cloud architecture with a standard cloud computing model.	According to the simulation results, fog computing layer deployment is advantageous since it lowers overall latency and boosts request satisfaction rates.
11.	Resource Allocation in Combined Fog-Cloud Scenarios by Using Artificial Intelligence[11]	Masoud Abedi , Mohammadreza Pourkiani	In contrast to cloud-based and fog-based techniques, the AITDA's primary trial demonstrates that this strategy significantly lowers response times and internet traffic.	In subsequent research, we propose to employ feature selection and online training techniques to decrease the number of inputs and enhance the function approximation method's accuracy, respectively. Additionally, we advise assessing how well the various function approximation techniques work in terms of forecasting the magnitude of the results and the reaction time.
12.	Combining ANTIBIOTIC with Fog Computing: ANTIBIOTIC 2.0[12]	Michele De Donno, Nicola Dragoni	ANTIBIOTIC 2.0 is an anti-malware program that uses fog computing to safeguard Internet of Things devices and solves the primary problems with its predecessor.	Antibiotic 1.0 is enhanced and improved by this unique method, which leverages fog computing to get over its primary drawbacks. and realizing the antimicrobial approach's full justification. Upcoming efforts will concentrate on ANTIBIOTIC 2.0 complete implementation, beginning with a proof-of-concept (PoC) and continuing to enhance the system's architecture, add new functionality, and refine current ones.
13.	Trade-off Model of Fog-Cloud Computing for Space Information Networks[13]	Jarred Michael Carter, Husnu S. Narman*, Ozlem Cosgun†, and Jinwei Liu‡	The combination of fog-cloud computing with space information networks is the main topic of this article. Our main research topics are the viability of fog cloud architecture in space information networks and the advantages of fog computing for the security of these networks.	The most crucial concerns concerning the encryption method, associated key management techniques, and the lengthy and fluctuating propagation latency resulting from the separation between nodes and satellites are the trade-offs between fog and cloud computing.
14.	Remote health monitoring system of elderly based on Fog to Cloud (F2C) computing[14]	Hafida Saidi, Nabila Labraoui, Ado Adamou Abba Ari, Djelloul Bouida	Fog to cloud computing is a fresh idea and cutting-edge strategy that helps improve the cloud's and fog computing's synergy to make managing senior health data easier.	Moving forward, we aim to address the issue of privacy ways by utilizing the F2C framework. Specifically, we will concentrate on implementing the suggested architecture through various encryption and access control strategies.

15.	Fog Computing in Appliance for Electrical Monitoring System in Greenhouse[15]	Nam Hoang Nguyen,Viet Hoang Duong	Energy use has become a significant problem. Over the past few decades, when emissions from unregulated Fossil fuel combustion have been the cause of climate change. In this research, the authors developed a system that uses the Fog computing concept to monitor the state of electrical appliances.	Data gathering and training take a lot of time with the present recognition algorithm. More precisely, we must gather information for 2n scenarios when there are n devices to identify. Thus, the authors' goal for their next work is to create an additional time-saving algorithm.
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CONCLUSION

Two cutting-edge technologies that have completely changed data processing, access, and storage are fog and cloud computing. Fog computing, particularly in real-time scenarios such as autonomous vehicles or industrial IoT applications, allows quicker processing and lower latency by bringing computation and storage resources closer to edge devices. It becomes more economical and efficient by lowering the demands for bandwidth and cloud server load. Users can store and retrieve data at any time and from any location with cloud computing, which offers on-demand access to a pool of computing resources housed in data centers. Moreover, it provides scalable solutions, enabling companies to flexibly distribute resources following their requirements. When combined, fog and cloud computing offer a complete and effective computing environment that lowers latency and meets real-time processing demands. The blending of fog and cloud computing will be necessary to support developing technologies and spur additional innovation across multiple industries as the number of connected devices increases and the amount of data generated increases rapidly.

FUTURE WORK

This study highlights the special qualities and possible uses of fog computing in healthcare while discussing current research on privacy and security concerns. The advantages of fog computing are emphasized, including how it can lessen network strain and modify sensor needs by offloading tasks between sensors and the cloud. It also necessitates the usage of thorough architectures that take into account a range of deployment scenarios and application use cases. Task scheduling and resource reallocation in smart manufacturing are the main topics of a suggested solution for assembly line terminal devices that analyze data in real-time. The outcomes of the experiments are encouraging, but problems with image positioning and cloud resource finiteness still require attention. Another method that is being developed addresses searchable encryption, organization, dynamic data collection, and data refining by combining fog and cloud computing for secure data storage and retrieval. It does, however, encounter difficulties, including privacy concerns and restricted methods for data retrieval. Fog offloading, which transfers resource-intensive tasks from devices with constrained resources to fog or cloud servers, is another topic covered in the study. While various algorithms are investigated for offloading schemas, including DQN and Q learning, issues related to security, mobility, multi-objective mechanisms, workload prediction, optimal policy selection, and offloading modelling remain to be resolved.

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